

Prevalence of multidrug-resistance of *Escherichia coli* in urinary tract infection patients visiting Rehman Medical Hospital, Peshawar, Pakistan

Bashir Aqib and Rehman Bilal^{1*}

Centre of Biotechnology and Microbiology, University of Peshawar, 25120, KPK, Pakistan

*Author for correspondence Email: bilal.cobam@gmail.com

Manuscript details:

Available online on <https://www.ijlsci.in>
ISSN: 2320-964X (Online)
ISSN: 2320-7817 (Print)

Cite this article as:

Bashir Aqib and Rehman Bilal (2022) Prevalence of multidrug-resistance of *Escherichia coli* in urinary tract infection patients visiting Rehman Medical Hospital, Peshawar, Pakistan, *Int. J. of Life Sciences*, Special Issue, A19: 39-49.

Article published in Special issue of Darwin - 2021: An international Conference (2nd one of the India's Biggest evolutionary Movements in Biology organized by Somaiya Vidyavihar & Riid) on 2nd to 5th December 2021.

Open Access This article is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

International License, which permits use, sharing, adaptation, distribution and reproduction in any medium or format, as long as you give appropriate credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if changes were made. The images or other third-party material in this article are included in the article's Creative Commons license, unless indicated otherwise in a credit line to the material. If material is not included in the article's Creative Commons license and your intended use is not permitted by statutory regulation or exceeds the permitted use, you will need to obtain permission directly from the copyright holder. To view a copy of this license, visit <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

ABSTRACT

Aims: The purpose of this study was to find out the prevalence of multi-drug resistance *E. coli* in urinary tract infection patients visiting Rehman medical hospital, tertiary care hospital in Peshawar, Pakistan.

Methodology: A total of 800 urine samples were collected from patients of all genders and all ages in 6 months whither 150 samples were positive for UTI. CLED Agar media was used to observe bacterial growth in urine samples followed by the biochemical test API10. The samples which showed bacterial growth were then subjected to MHA media to detect the sensitivity/susceptibility of antibiotics using antibiotic disc where more than three drugs showed resistance to the tested antibiotics.

Results: 100 out of 150 samples were positive for MDR and 50 samples were non-MDR. Of the agent's tested Fosfomycin (15.3%), Amikacin (16 %), and Tazobactam (18.7%) showed the lowest resistance, and Amoxicillin /clavulanic acid (74.7%), Cefepime (70 %) and Levofloxacin (62.7%) showed the highest resistance. Among the other tested agents in the current study Cotrimaxlole showed 47.3%, Salbactam 24.7%, Cefipime 70 %, Ampicillin 54%, Ceftraixone 43.3 % Fosfomycin 15.3 % and Norfloxacin 54 % resistance respectively.

Conclusions: The prevalence of MDR antibiotics that were not resistant to *E. coli* a decade ago was found to be emerging gradually to an alarming situation which is most likely due to excessive usage, partial medication, and self-medication along with other factors.

Keywords: MDR (Multi Drug Resistance), CLED (Cysteine Lactose Electrolyte Deficient), MHA (Mueller Hinton Agar), API (Analytical Profile Index).

INTRODUCTION

Urinary tract infections (UTIs) represent a major public health problem. They are one of the most familiar infections caused by bacteria and they can be found in the general population and hospital-acquired known as nosocomial infections. *Escherichia coli*; commonly found as a commensal inhabitant of the gastrointestinal tract, is the primary cause of UTI.

Infections that are caused by the Enterobacteriaceae family members are among the foremost and primary causes of hospital admission and are associated with diseases and deaths in children. Infections caused by these bacteria in low-income or developing countries have been successfully cured with easily accessible and affordable antibiotics (Guiral *et al.* 2018).

Over the years, *Escherichia coli* like any other Enterobacteriaceae member has become resistant with an increased rate to antibiotics, (Nabti *et al.* 2019). With the excessive growth of multidrug-resistant strains, the effectiveness of the antibiotics that were effective in early times has greatly reduced resulting in the foundation of antibiotics that are of broad spectrum nature like fluoroquinolones and third-generation cephalosporin which are usually unaffordable in most developing or low-income countries (Guiral *et al.* 2018).

1.1 *E. coli*

Escherichia coli is a rod-shaped gram-negative microorganism belonging to the Enterobacteriaceae family. Naturally, it is commensally residing in the colon of human beings. It also lives in the colon of animals such as lizards, birds, and higher organisms as well (Alhashash, 2015). *E. coli* normally get rid of its host via stools to the environment where *E. coli* can make their living for days or months. Survival of *E. coli* in its secondary surrounding depends on several conditions for example food, water humidity, and temperature as well (van Elsas *et al.* 2011). As the bacterium (*E. coli*) is essentially an inhabitant of the intestine, living outside the natural host or inhabitant is that's why somewhat limited if the occurrence of *E. coli* is suspected somewhere else like water or food may be the indication of fecal contamination or mal hygienic practice (Odonkor & Ampofo, 2013).

1.2 Causes of *E. coli*

E. coli most frequently can cause Urinary tract infections (UTIs) which are the commonest bacterial infection in people of old age. Urinary tract infection can be defined as the existence of pathogenic bacteria (*ECOLI*) (10^5 CFU/mL) in excreted urine (Mishra, M. P *et al.* 2016). *Escherichia coli* can also cause an extra-intestinal infection that can be defined as extra-intestinal pathogenic *E. coli* 'ExPEC'. This group arises from the understanding that genotypic and phenotypic differences among the *E. coli*

encounter a majority of extra-intestinal diseases, Disease includes UTI, meningitis in newborns, hospital-acquired pneumonia, biliary and GIT infections, septic arthritis, etc... A simple infection needs to populate in non-sterile location, for example, the gastrointestinal tract and then attack the sterile site, besides these, non-pathogenic of *E. coli* can create infection whenever normal immune defenses of the host compromises. For example, UTIs due to catheters, peritonitis, etc (Alhashash, 2015).

Worldwide it is calculated that 150 million UTIs annually reach more than 6 billion dollars due to healthcare costs (Stamm, W. E., & Norrby, S. R. 2001). For the majority of people especially adults UTIs are an issue that requires brief antibacterial treatment, individuals with pyelonephritis especially older ones can lead to bacteremia, long-term hospitalization, antimicrobial therapy, and treatments, reducing functional status and death. According to a study it is calculated that globally about 150 million UTIs have been reported yearly (Stamm, 2001). It also involves the most common hospital-acquired infection in the majority of hospitals which accounts for about 35% of all hospital-acquired infections. The commonest pathogen in UTI (*E. coli*) was isolated from uncomplicated urinary tract infection isolates (Hassan *et al.* 2011).

Globally it has been reported that pathogens of UTIs (*E. coli*) have been showing resistance to conventional drugs. Even Resistance has also emerged to newer drugs (Taneja *et al.* 2008). Resistance to antimicrobial and observation is important to understand the severity of the problem and to rule out and guide the empirical selection of antibacterial agents for treating the affected individuals. The purpose of our study is to understand the current frequency and phenotype of multidrug-resistant strains in between UTI-causing *E. coli* isolates against commonly used antimicrobial pathogens.

Drugs like antibiotics have been used to kill bacteria, which is causing illness and disease. Antibiotics have made a major contribution to human health. Decades ago many diseases once killed individuals can now be treated readily with antibiotics. However, some of the microbes become resistant to antibiotics.

Resistant microbes are those bacteria that cannot be stopped or killed by antibiotics. They are still making their

living and even replicate in the presence of antibiotics. Those Bacteria resistant to more than one antibiotic are known as multi-resistant organisms (Ikram *et al.* 2015).

1.3 How bacteria show resistance to antibiotic

Antibiotic usage leads to the development of bacteria which becomes resistant to antibiotics. Each time when an individual takes antibiotic, which kill sensitive bacteria, some germs which show resistance to those antibiotics may leave behind leading to their growth and multiplication. Self-medication and repeated usage of partial treatment of antibiotics are basic and primary causes of the increased number of bacteria showing resistance to antibiotics (Barbosa and Levy, 2000). Infections caused by bacteria are usually treated with antibiotics, which are not often effective against illnesses caused by viral pathogens like flu, sore throats, and the common cold. Excessive usage of antibiotics leads to the spread of resistance to antibiotics. The prime and most vital factor for overcoming the spread of resistance is to use antibiotics wisely avoiding partial treatment, self-medication, and less use of antibiotics (Rao, 1998).

Resistance to antibiotics takes place when bacteria change in a few manners which makes drugs less effective or even eliminates the effectiveness of antibiotics, chemical compounds, or other retailers that are used for the treatment of infections or to prevent infectious illnesses. The bacteria live to tell the tale and hold on to multiply inflicting more damage. The microorganism can try this via several mechanisms. Some of the bacteria broaden the capacity to neutralize the used antibiotic before it could cause some consequences, while others can unexpectedly reject the drug still some other bacteria can change the site where the respective antibiotic could attack which leads to the prevention of bacteria from any type of change in their characteristics so it cannot affect the characteristics (Cunha, 2020).

Antibiotics used to cure any infectious disease primarily kill or tend to inhibit the boom of vulnerable microorganisms. Occasionally one of the microorganisms survives because it has the required competency to neutralize or inhibit the effect of the antibiotic; that leads to the growth and multiplication of that bacterium can replace all the killed bacteria. Subjection to the antibiotics, therefore, offers selective strain, making the surviving

microorganism to become resistant. Moreover, bacteria that were normally at risk of an antibiotic can collect resistance through mutation in their genetic material or using a way of obtaining portions of DNA that code for the resistance homes making them different from other bacteria. The DNA that codes for resistance can be grouped in a single without difficulty transferable package deal. Because of this bacteria can emerge as proof against many antimicrobial retailers because of the switch of one piece of DNA (Vedantam and Hecht, 2003).

1.4 MDR

Escherichia coli (*E. coli*) have transcended to a stage of antimicrobial resistance where humans are fronting intense scientific challenges in the shape of urinary tract infections (UTIs), surgical wound infections, and neonatal sepsis. *E. coli* are offering a brief spread of resistance genes among traces through horizontal transfer in particular by using plasmids. Production of beta-lactamases is the essential defense tool of Enterobacteriaceae against β lactam antibiotics. These microorganisms are capable of decreasing the efficacy of modern prolonged spectrum cephalosporins except cephamycins and carbapenems with the aid of the production of plasmid-mediated extended-spectrum beta-lactamases (ESBLs) (Iqbal *et al.* 2002).

Multi-drug resistant microorganisms cause more complications ensuing in reduced usefulness of high-quality remedies (Karlowsky *et al.* 2001). The control of UTIs because of multi-drug resistant microorganisms may be hard mainly due to the common emergence of resistance to new antimicrobials and the unfold of resistant bacteria past hospitals into the network which include nursing houses (Wiener *et al.* 1999). These facilities can act as reservoirs of these MDROs that may then be transmitted to acute hospitals in prone populations, consisting of nursing domestic citizens wherein besides the point remedy of asymptomatic bacteremia may be a particular problem, UTI's can have a better occurrence of resistance to antimicrobials along with ciprofloxacin, cephazolin, and nitrofurantoin. Mortality is better following bacteremia with traces proof against antimicrobials than with traces touchy to antimicrobials, although that is maximumly probable because of irrelevant empiric antimicrobial remedy as

opposed to an association with multiplied virulence of the *e coli* strains (Ikram *et al.* 2015).

Threat elements for the prognosis of UTIs resulting from Multi-drug resistant microorganisms can be labeled as character factors, predisposing elements, and bacterial factors (Richards, 2004). The person or demographic characteristics that may affect the danger of colonization of the urinary tract with MDROs encompass older age, female sex, a record of UTIs and diagnoses of dementia or poor purposeful level, diabetes, and prostatic ailment. Predisposing or healthcare-associated elements related to an extended danger of network-obtained MDROs within the urinary tract encompass invasive tactics which include urinary catheterization, preceding hospitalization, housing in a nursing home, and previous publicity to antimicrobials (Wiener *et al.* 1999).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Study design

Descriptive cross-sectional study

2.2 Study setting

The study was conducted at Rehman College of allied health sciences Peshawar, Pathology Department, Rehman Medical Institute (RMI) Peshawar, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KP).

2.3 Study duration

The study was carried out from December to April 2021.

2.4 Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Both male and female patients with different age groups have complaints of, fever pain or a burning sensation when urinating. Nausea and vomiting. A patient who had previously taken antibiotic were omitted.

2.5 Collection of blood samples

In the present study, 800 urine samples were collected from all outdoor (OPD) and indoor (IPD) patients who visited RMI from both genders of all ages.

2.6 Media used in the research work

In the current study, Different types of culture media were used; CLED agar, MacConkey agar, and Mueller Hinton agar.

2.6.1 CLED

(Cystine Lactose electrolyte deficient) agar was prepared as per manufacturer instructions and according to the composition mentioned in Table 2.1. The required amount of media was dissolved in distilled water, boiled to fully dissolve the agar, and then autoclaved i.e. 15 psi at 121°C for 15 minutes. The medium's pH was adjusted to 7.2 and then introduced to the sterile Petri dish under sterile conditions for solidification. The plates were kept at 37°C for 24 hours for sterility check and only sterile ones were used for experiments.

Table 2.1 Composition of CLED agar media

Ingredients	Amount (gm/L)
Lactose	10.0
Pancreatic Digest of Gelatin	4.0
Pancreatic Digest of Casein	4.0
Beef Extract	3.0
L-Cystine	0.128
Bromothymol Blue	0.02
Agar	15
Distilled Water	1 Liter

2.6.2 MacConkey agar

MacConkey agar was prepared as per manufacturer instructions and according to the composition mentioned in Table 2.2. The required amount of media was dissolved in distilled water, boiled to fully dissolve the agar, and then autoclaved i.e. 15 psi at 121°C for 15 minutes. The medium's pH was adjusted to 6.8 and then introduced to the sterile Petri dish under sterile conditions for solidification. The plates were kept at 37°C for 24 hours for sterility check and only sterile ones were used for experiments.

Table 2.2 Composition of MacConkey agar

Ingredients	Amount (gm/L)
Protease peptone (meat and casein)	3
Peptone (Pancreatic digest of gelatin)	17
Lactose monohydrate	10
Bile salts	1.5
Sodium chloride	5
Neutral red	0.03
Crystal Violet	0.001
Agar	13.5
Distilled Water	1 liter

2.6.3 Mueller Hinton agar

The Ingredients of Mueller Hinton agar are given in **Table 2.3**. As per instructions of the manufacturer, the desired amount of media was added to an appropriate amount of distilled water and heated to liquefy agar. The medium's pH was shifted to 7.3 after sterilization i.e. 121°C at 15 psi for 15 minutes. Solid plates were then prepared after pouring the media into the sterile Petri plates under sterile conditions. Plates were then kept at 37°C for 24 hours to check their sterility and only sterile ones were used for experiments.

Table 2.3 Composition of Mueller Hinton Agar

Ingredients	Amount (gm/L)
Acid Hydrolysate of Casein	17.50
Beef extract	2.0
Starch	1.5
Agar	17.0
Distilled Water	1 liter

2.7 Staining techniques

Staining is a procedure generally used for the detection of bacterial cells after absorbing a specific dye. It is a confirmatory technique to know whether the bacterial cells are rods, cocci, spirals, etc. when viewed under a microscope.

2.7.1 Principle of Gram staining

Using this technique, a researcher can differentiate bacterial colonies belonging to two domains i.e. Gram-negative and Gram-positive. The principle of this procedure is based on the changes in the characteristics of the cell wall of bacteria. Gram-positive bacterial cell wall, being rich in peptidoglycan, retains the crystal violet dye and becomes purple, while the Gram-negative bacterial cell wall has a low content of peptidoglycan and an additional lipid layer in the cell wall. These features make the cell wall be stained with the counter stain i.e. safranin and not the primary stain (crystal violet) which is washed out with the decolorizing agent used in the procedure.

The morphology of all bacterial isolates in this study was examined after performing Gram staining protocols.

2.7.2 Procedure

1. A loop full of colonies from bacteria grown on an agar plate was mixed in saline water to prepare a smear which was placed on a clean and grease-free slide.

2. The smear on the slide was fixed using gentle heating.
3. Then smear was gently flooded with dye i.e. crystal violet and then rinsed after 1 minute with running water.
4. Then the Gram's iodine was applied on the slide and washed for 1 min.
5. The smear was then decolorized for 5 to 10 seconds with the application of 95% ethyl alcohol till the alcohol almost cleared the smear and then rinsed using tap water.
6. The slide was then flooded with counter-stain (safranin) and was rinsed with tap water after 45 seconds. The slide was then dried with bibulous paper and was viewed using a light microscope under oil immersion.

Table 2.4 The composition of Gram stain.

Gram Crystal Violet	Amount (gm/L)
Crystal Violet (Primary stain)	20.0
Ammonium Oxalate	8.0
Methanol	200.0 mL
Gram Iodine (Iodine Crystals)	3.33
Potassium Iodide	6.67
Gram Decolorize (Ethanol/ Acetone)	500.0 mL
Safranin (Counter stain)	0.25 g

2.8 Biochemical tests

Biochemical tests can distinguish between bacterial species based on certain proteins in a bacterial isolate. Different biochemical tests were used in the current study for the identification of *Escherichia coli* and are mentioned in the following paragraphs.

2.8.1 Urease test

The urease test is based on the activity of the urease enzyme and is useful to distinguish enterobacteria. The species that have urease activity include *Proteus* and *Yersinia enterocolitis* while *Salmonellae* and *Shigellae* are urease negative. Bacterial species producing urease enzyme produces ammonia and carbon dioxide from urea as substrate. Changes in the pH of the incubating medium indicate the presence of ammonia which turned into an alkaline state.

2.8.1.1 Procedure

The surface of the slant of the media was streaked with 18-24 hours old culture and incubated at 37°C for 24

hours. Usually, the urease-positive organisms changed the color of the slant to bright pink while there is no color change in urease-negative organisms. After a short period of incubation, a clear difference between the slant and butt was observed.

Table 2.5 Reagents of Christensen's Medium use for urease test

Ingredients	Amount (gm/L)
Peptone	1.0
Sodium chloride	5.0
Dipotassium hydrogen phosphate	2.0
Phenol red (1 in 500 aqueous solutions)	6 ml
Agar	20
Distilled water	1 liter
Glucose 10 percent sterile solution	10 ml
Urea 20 percent sterile solution	100 ml

2.8.2 Citrate Test

The citrate test differentiates *Enterobacteria* from other bacteria and works on the consumption of citrate and ammonia as the only carbon and nitrogen sources, respectively. A change in turbidity and color from light green to blue indicates microbial growth inside the media.

2.8.2.1 Procedure

The medium was inoculated with the microbial colony and then kept for four days at 35-37°C with regular checking after 24 hrs period for color alteration and growth. To avoid contamination inside the medium, carbon particles and a regularly flamed wire were used.

Table 2.6 Reagents of the Simmons Citrate Agar for Citrate test

Ingredients	Amount (gm/L)
Sodium chloride	5.0
Magnesium sulfate	0.2
Ammonium dihydrogen Phosphate	1.0
Sodium citrate	5.0
Bromothymol blue	(0.2%)
Distilled water	1 liter

2.8.3 Triple Sugar Iron Agar Test (TSI)

This TSI agar enables the microbiologist to distinguish the microbes among the groups of *Enterobacteriaceae* based

on their capability to consume three types of sugars i.e. lactose, sucrose, and glucose present in the media. All *Enterobacteriaceae* are known as Gram-negative bacilli that only ferment glucose and produces acid and are thus different from other Gram-negative gut bacillus species. The differentiation can be due to modifications in hydrogen sulfide production and carbohydrate fermentation patterns by the several groups of intestinal microbes.

2.8.3.1 Procedure

The TSI media was prepared and 5 ml of it was distributed into different test tubes. The tubes were then sterilized and placed in slanting positions to make slants. All the bacterial isolates were streaked on the TSI agar slants and also stabbed inoculation was performed at the bottom with a sterilized loop. TSI tubes were then kept for 24 hours at 37°C.

Table 2.7 Reagents of the Triple Sugar Iron Media

Ingredients	Amount (gm/L)
Yeast extract	3.0
Peptone	15
Protease peptone	5.0
Lactose	10.0
Saccharose	10.0
Glucose	1.0
Ferrous sulfate	0.2
Sodium chloride	5.0
Sodium thiosulphate	0.3
Phenol red	0.024
Agar	12
Distilled water	Liter

2.9 Measuring Antimicrobial sensitivity pattern

The antibiotic susceptibility of the bacterial species was measured according to the Kirby-Bauer disc diffusion protocol and the results were then deduced in the light of recommendations provided by the Clinical and Laboratory Standard Institute (CLSI). The antibiotics used in the current study are mentioned in table 2.8.

2.9.1 Disc Diffusion Technique

The disc diffusion method described by Kirby Bauer (Betty et al., 1998; CLSI, 2006) was used for measuring the *in-vitro* susceptibility pattern. A lawn of pure culture was

Table 2.8 List of antibiotic discs used in the current study

Name of the antibiotic	Family	Concentration (μg)
Nitrofurantoin	Nitro furans	100
Ampicillin	Penicillin	10
Amoxicillin/clavulanic acid	Penicillin	20
Fosfomycin	novel class	50
Norfloxacin	Quinolone	10
Ciprofloxacin	Fluoroquinolone	5
Clotrimazole	Sulfonamide	25
Gentamycin	Aminoglycoside	10
Amikacin	Aminoglycoside	30
Piperacillin Tazobactam	Penicillin	110
Imipenem	Carbapenem	10
Ceftazidime	Cephalosporin	30
Cefepime	Cephalosporin	30
Ceftriaxone	Cephalosporin	30
Colistin	Polymyxin	10

made on sterile MHA plates and an antibiotic disc was placed on the plates. Negative control was also run. Both the positive and negative samples were kept for at least 24 hours at 37°C. On the very next day, zone(s) formed due to growth inhibition were calculated in millimeters (mm). The susceptibility (sensitive, intermediate, or resistant) of each drug was measured using the guidelines CLSI.

RESULTS

This study was conducted in the microbiology section of the RMI laboratory where a total of 150 samples were analyzed to assess the current breadth of multidrug resistance coli present in UTI patients. The overall rates of resistance for these 150 samples analyzed are provided according to age status, gender, and MDR statu.

Fig 1.0: Illustrates the frequency of age status of the analyzed samples where 34 samples ($n=150$) are children and 116 samples ($n=150$) are adults.

Fig 1.1: Illustrates the frequency of gender among analyzed samples where 106 samples ($n=150$) are males and 44 samples ($n=150$) are females.

Fig 1.2: Illustrates the frequency of positive and negative samples according to the MDR status of all analyzed samples. 48 samples (32%) out of the total 150 samples are MDR positive and 101 samples (67.3 %) out of 150 samples are MDR negative.

Percent resistivity and sensitivity of Escherichia coli against selected antibiotics

Fig 1.3: Illustrates the sensitivity and resistivity of the total 150 analyzed samples. The overall rates of resistance for the *E coli* isolates analyzed are provided in above figure 1.3. Of the agents tested Fosfomycin (15.3%), Amikacin (16 %), and Tazobactam (18.7%) showed the lowest resistance, and Amoxycillin /clavulanic acid (74.7%), Cefepime (70 %) and Levofloxacin (62.7%) showed the highest resistance.

DISCUSSION

This study was carried out to investigate the prevalence of Multidrug resistance among patients with urinary tract infections at Rehman medical institute, a tertiary healthcare hospital (Peshawar Pakistan). A total of 150 samples were collected from the patients with UTI. Among

the 150 *E. coli* isolates 34 (22.7%) samples were collected from the children and 116 (77.3 %) samples were collected from the adults.

This collected data showed a much higher degree of *E. coli* resistance to different antibiotics. Of the agents tested Fosfomycin (15.3%), Amikacin (16 %), and Tazobactam

(18.7%) showed the lowest resistance, and Amoxicillin/clavulanic acid (74.7%), Cefepime (70 %) and levofloxacin (62.7%) showed the highest resistance. In the current study, the susceptibility pattern for *E coli* strains was checked to determine the effectiveness of prescribed antibiotics for the treatment of infections which showed that imipenem was only 75 % sensitive. The results obtained showed a lower degree of sensitivity compared to a study done in turkey where *imipenem* and *meropenem* were the most effective antibiotics with 100% sensitivity for *E coli* (savaset *et al.*, 2006). Furthermore, our study unfolded that *Ecoli* showed 77.3 % sensitivity to Amikacin. A study done in Nepal showed a slightly higher susceptibility pattern (87%) to Amikacin (Das *et al.*, 2006). (Guiral *et al.* 2018).

Amikacin an aminoglycoside antibiotic is only administered through intravenous injections. As this drug is only used in during severe infections which could be the reason for its sensitivity as infrequent usage of this antibiotic leads to make *Ecoli* more sensitive to it compared to Gentamycin 64.7 % Nitrofurantoin (70 %) Tazobactam (74 %) respectively which are usually prescribed against *Ecoli* causing infections.

The rise in the multi-drug resistant organisms leads to a major public health and therapeutic challenge to clinicians throughout the world. Commonly found gram-negative bacteria that encounter human health can get cross-resistance to many agents used as an antibacterial leading to the reduction or complete failure of the treatment (Iqbal *et al.* 2002).

In our study *E coli* was almost 75% resistant to more than one tested antibiotic such as Amoxicillin, and Cefepime. However, a study conducted in Karachi, Pakistan showed that *E coli* was 92% resistant to one or more antibiotics (Saeed *et al.* 2009). A study conducted in Tamil Nadu, India reported that *E coli* commensally isolates were 42% resistant to one or more antibiotics (Mathai *et al.* 2008). Another study conducted by (Al Tawafiq, 2006) reports that 2-29% *E coli* isolates were resistant to one or more antibiotics. The findings of our results are more or less the same as all the mentioned results in the neighboring or far-off countries (Iqbal *et al.* 2002).

Our study revealed that MDR *E coli* were mainly resistant to antibiotics belonging to the B-Lactam group antibiotics

such as Amoxicillin/Clavulanic acid and Ampicillin all three sharing the same class and were least ineffective against *E coli* followed by the second-class antibiotics like cephalosporin's and fluoroquinolone which showed resistance to MDR *E coli*. A study conducted in UAE (United Arab Emirates) that Cephalosporin and Cotrimoxazole were the most usual antibiotics falling in the MDR *E coli*-resistant group. (Tanvir *et al.* 2012).

Among all the tested antibiotics non-β-lactam showed good activity such as Gentamicin showed sensitivity and resistance with 64% and 34% respectively in the currently conducted study, which is more than the susceptible activity reported in Israel (29%) and India (36%) (Tankhiwale *et al.*, 2004; Colodner *et al.*, 2007). This might be the reason for the excessive use of Gentamicin in India and Israel as compared to Pakistan (Iqbal *et al.* 2002).

Among the other tested agents in the current study cotrimaxoloe showed 47.3%, Salbactam 24.7%, Cifpime 70 %, Ampicillin 54%, ceftriaxone 43.3 % fosfomycin 15.3 % and Norfloxacin 54 % resistance respectively. Furthermore, our study revealed that Fosfomycin was the least resistant of all the mentioned tested antibiotics. In a study conducted by Habeeb *et al.* 2012 resistance for Fosfomycin was undetected in any of the 2005 isolates but later on 5.8% was found resistant among 2009,10 urinary tract isolates. Moreover, Imipenem resistance was not reported from the urinary tract isolates 2009-10 showed resistance, and none was seen detected in 2005 isolates. But, to worry is that not much or less resistance was present in 2005 but now these are arising increasingly. The current level of Imipenem resistance 21.3 % in the current study is comparable to the new reports generated worldwide. Furthermore, resistance to Fosfomycin is raised to higher (15.3 %) levels as compared with recent reports (Ramírez *et al.* 2018).

Several factors may be the prime cause that led to the resistance at much higher levels such as the wrong usage of antibiotics by the doctors or physicians while prescribing the medication or practitioners who lack the basic skills, partial medication, or self-medication by people (as in Brazil antibiotics can be purchased without a physician's prescription), and improper surveillance due to the least of knowledgeable generated from usual susceptibility testing for antimicrobials, such as reports or

results generated from low income or developing countries (Ramírez *et al.* (2018).

In the studies followed previously for susceptibility in Pakistan, susceptibility patterns were not arranged or characterized according to age, so no local statistics were available to compare our current study data. However, a study conducted in Spain reported that an age more than 64 was highlighted to be a risk factor, with various other factors, for high resistance to antibiotics against *E. coli* (Iqbal *et al.* 2002).

Though we were not able to find out the prime reasons for such high resistance in our study sex, previously taken antibiotic treatment, hospital infections vs. infections acquired by the general population, urinary catheterization and abnormalities found in the urinary tract may be the prime factors leading to this resistance but further studies at large scale are needed to be conducted to find out about these variables acting as independent risk factors.

Acknowledgment

The author(s) are thankful to Dr. Maria Khattak Head of the Microbiology Department at Rehman Medical Institute, Peshawar, Pakistan, for providing necessary laboratory facilities and also to Dr. Sumaira Afzal Director of Centre of Biotechnology and Microbiology, University of Peshawar, KP, Pakistan for providing help and support in research work.

Conflict of Interest: The author(s) declares no conflict of Interest.

REFERENCES

Alhashash, F. A. (n.d.). *Populations of Escherichia coli in clinical samples of Urinary Tract Infections and Bacteraemia* [Ph.D. Thesis]. Nottingham Trent University.

Barbosa, T. M., & Levy, S. B. (2000). The impact of antibiotic use on resistance development and persistence. *Drug resistance updates : reviews and commentaries in antimicrobial and anticancer chemotherapy*, 3(5), 303–311. <https://doi.org/10.1054/drup.2000.0167>

Dr. Cunha is an Affiliated Assistant Professor of Medicine at the University of Miami, Miller School of Medicine. He has served as a Clinical Assistant Professor in the Department of Family Medicine at Nova Southeastern University College of Osteopathic Medicine, Fort. Lauderdale, FL. He also served on the Undergraduate Medical Education

Committee for the American College of Osteopathic Emergency Physicians (ACOEP).

- Guiral, E., Pons, M. J., Vubil, D., Marí-Almirall, M., Sigaúque, B., Soto, S. M., Alonso, P. L., Ruiz, J., Vila, J., & Mandomando, I. (2018). Epidemiology and molecular characterization of multidrug-resistant *Escherichia coli* isolates harboring *bla*_{CTX-M} group 1 extended-spectrum β -lactamases causing bacteremia and urinary tract infection in Manhica, Mozambique. *Infection and drug resistance*, 11, 927–936. <https://doi.org/10.2147/IDR.S153601>
- Hassan, S., Jamal, S. A., & Kamal, M. (2011). OCCURRENCE OF MULTIDRUG RESISTANT AND ESBL PRODUCING E.COLI CAUSING URINARY TRACT INFECTIONS. *Https://Www.Semanticscholar.Org/*. Retrieved April 10, 2021, from <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/OCCURRENCE-OF-MULTIDRUG-RESISTANT-AND-ESBL-E.COLI-Hassan-jamal/7fad0c4fb3cf40b486be0003546827fa8c09b28a>
- Ikram, R., Psutka, R., Carter, A., & Priest, P. (2015, June 9). An outbreak of multi-drug resistant *Escherichia coli* urinary tract infection in an elderly population: a case-control study of risk factors. *BMC Infectious Diseases*, 15(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12879-015-0974-0>
- Iqbal, M., Patel, I. K., Shah, S. H., Ain, Q., Barney, N., Kiani, Q., Rabbani, K. Z., Zaidi, G., & Mehdi, B. (2002). Susceptibility patterns of *Escherichia coli*: prevalence of multidrug-resistant isolates and extended spectrum beta-lactamase phenotype. *JPMA. The Journal of the Pakistan Medical Association*, 52(9), 407–411.
- Karlowsky, J. A., Jones, M. E., Thornsberry, C., Critchley, I., Kelly, L. J., & Sahm, D. F. (2001, August). Prevalence of antimicrobial resistance among urinary tract pathogens isolated from female outpatients across the US in 1999. *International Journal of Antimicrobial Agents*, 18(2), 121–127. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0924-8579\(01\)00369-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0924-8579(01)00369-7)
- Mishra, M. P., Sarangi, R., & Padhy, R. N. (2016, May). Prevalence of multidrug resistant uropathogenic bacteria in pediatric patients of a tertiary care hospital in eastern India. *Journal of Infection and Public Health*, 9(3), 308–314. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jiph.2015.10.002>
- Nabti, L. Z., Sahli, F., Radji, N., Mezaghcha, W., Semara, L., Aberkane, S., Lounnas, M., Solassol, J., Didelot, M. N., Jean-Pierre, H., Dumont, Y., & Godreuil, S. (2019). High Prevalence of Multidrug-Resistant *Escherichia coli* in Urine Samples from Inpatients and Outpatients at a Tertiary Care Hospital in Sétif, Algeria. *Microbial drug resistance (Larchmont, N.Y.)*, 25(3), 386–393. <https://doi.org/10.1089/mdr.2018.0314>
- Odonkor, S. T., & Ampofo, J. K. (2013, June 11). *Escherichia coli* as an indicator of bacteriological quality of water: an overview. *Microbiology Research*, 4(1), 2. <https://doi.org/10.4081/mr.2013.e2>
- Ramírez-Castillo, F.Y., Moreno-Flores, A.C., Avelar-González, F.J. *et al.* (2018). An evaluation of multidrug-resistant *Escherichia coli* isolates in urinary tract infections

- from Aguascalientes, Mexico: cross-sectional study. *Ann Clin Microbiol Antimicrob*
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12941-018-0286-5>
- Rao G. G. (1998). Risk factors for the spread of antibiotic-resistant bacteria. *Drugs*, 55(3), 323-330.
<https://doi.org/10.2165/00003495-199855030-00001>
- Richards C. L. (2004). Urinary tract infections in the frail elderly: issues for diagnosis, treatment and prevention. *International urology and nephrology*, 36(3), 457-463. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11255-004-4870-6>
- Stamm, W., & Norrby, S. (2001b, March). Urinary Tract Infections: Disease Panorama and Challenges. *The Journal of Infectious Diseases*, 183(s1), S1-S4.
<https://doi.org/10.1086/318850>
- Tanvir, R., Hafeez, R., & Hasnain, S. (2012). Prevalence of Multiple Drug Resistant Escherichia coli in Patients of Urinary Tract Infection Registering at a Diagnostic Laboratory in Lahore, Pakistan. *Pakistan Journal of Zoology*, 44, 707-712.
- Stamm, W., & Norrby, S. (2001, March). Urinary Tract Infections: Disease Panorama and Challenges. *The Journal of Infectious Diseases*, 183(s1), S1-S4. <https://doi.org/10.1086/318850>
- Taneja, N., Rao, P., Arora, J., & Dogra, A. (2008). <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/18316858/>. *Pubmed.Gov*. Retrieved April 1, 2021, from <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/18316858/>
- van Elsas, J. D., Semenov, A. V., Costa, R., & Trevors, J. T. (2010, June 24). Survival of Escherichia coli in the environment: fundamental and public health aspects. *The ISME Journal*, 5(2), 173-183. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ismej.2010.80>
- Vedantam, G., & Hecht, D. W. (2003). Antibiotics and anaerobes of gut origin. *Current Opinion in Microbiology*, 6(5), 457-461. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mib.2003.09.006>
- Wiener, J. Quinn, J. P., Bradford, P. A., Goering, R. V., Nathan, C., Bush, K., & Weinstein, R. A. (1999). Multiple antibiotic-resistant Klebsiella and Escherichia coli in nursing homes. *JAMA*, 281(6), 517-523.
<https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.281.6.517>